

THE USE OF OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES AT UNIVERSITY OF LIBRARY STUDIES AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

DECriS project (Digital Education for Crisis Situations: Times When There is no Alternative) was accepted within the Erasmus+ Call launched in September 2020 supporting digital education readiness and creative skills. Project DECriS (<http://decris.ffos.hr/>, Contract number: 2020-1-HR01-KA226-HE-094685), started on 1st of March 2021 and will run for a duration of two years. Digital Education (DE) has the potential to provide better teaching and learning opportunities, especially in regards to the unpredictable circumstances such as COVID-19, which revealed that many higher education institutions (HEIs) faced problems of technical, socio-psychological and didactic nature. The partners' consortium includes: University of Osijek, Croatia (coordinator); University of Barcelona, Spain; University of Hildesheim, Germany; University of Library Studies and Information Technologies, Bulgaria, and University of Zagreb Computer Centre, Croatia and four associate partners. The project' target groups are students and teachers at partner HEIs and European HEIs that offer programs in Library and Information Science (L)IS, which are approached widely in regards to the use of Open Educational Resources (OERs) and ways for promoting, enriching and improving of digital education for crisis situations, and beyond.

The paper presents research results from a Survey, titled State-of-the-play of the use of OERs at European HEIs during the COVID-19 pandemic, implemented at University of Library Studies and Information Technologies (ULSIT), Bulgaria in June 2021 within the frame of DECriS project. The aim of this research is to identify state-of-play regarding the use of digital education and open educational resources in the context of COVID-19 pandemic on institutional level. The first part of our observations refers to the issue of digital education; the second part investigates the degrees of implementation and modes of use of open educational resources; and the third part explores the issue of institutional support provided to departments, lecturers and students regarding digital education and open educational resources. All three issues are assessed both in general and in the context of COVID-19 pandemic - the learning challenges, which we faced at AY 2019/2020 (summer semester) and AY 2020/2021. The analysis of the findings resulted in the creation of recommendations to be used as the basis for further reflection on the institutional DE quality assurance policy and the improvement of the Quality of Education Management System at ULSIT.

Keywords: Open Educational Resources, Digital education, University of Library Studies and Information Technologies, Bulgaria, DECriS Erasmus+ Project

1 INTRODUCTION

DECriS project (Digital Education for Crisis Situations: Times When There is no Alternative) was accepted within the Erasmus+ Call launched in September 2020 supporting digital education readiness and creative skills. The project started on 1st of March 2021 and has a duration of two years. Digital Education (DE) has the potential to provide better teaching and learning opportunities, especially in regards to the unpredictable circumstances such as COVID-19, which revealed that many higher education institutions (HEIs) faced problems of technical, socio-psychological and didactic nature. The partners' consortium includes: University of Osijek, Croatia (coordinator); University of Barcelona, Spain; University of Hildesheim, Germany; University of Library Studies and Information Technologies, Bulgaria, and University of Zagreb Computer Centre, Croatia and four associate partners. The project' target groups are students and teachers at partner HEIs and European HEIs that offer programs in Library and Information Science (L)IS, which are approached widely in regards to the use of Open Educational Resources (OERs) and ways for promoting, enriching and improving DE for crisis situations, and beyond (DECriS, 2021).

2 METHODOLOGY AND DEFINITIONS

The paper presents research results from a Survey, titled State-of-the-play of the use of OERs at European HEIs during the COVID-19 pandemic, implemented at University of Library Studies and Information Technologies (ULSIT), Bulgaria in June 2021 within the frame of DECriS project. The aim of this research is to identify state-of-play regarding the use of DE and open educational resources in the context of COVID-19 pandemic on institutional level.

In order to facilitate more comprehensive understanding of the topic researched, definitions of digital education and open educational resources, which DECriS research team use are the following: *Digital Education (DE)* – it is the innovative use of digital tools and technologies during teaching and learning, and is often referred to as Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL) or e-Learning. Exploring the use of digital technologies gives educators the opportunity to design engaging learning opportunities in the courses they teach, and these can take the form of blended or fully online courses and programmes (Institute for Academic Development, The University of Edinburgh); and *Open Educational Resources (OER)* – they are teaching, learning and research materials in any medium – digital or otherwise – that reside in the public domain or have been released under an open license that permits no-cost access, use, adaptation and redistribution by others with no or limited restrictions. OER form part of 'Open Solutions', alongside Free and Open Source software (FOSS), Open Access (OA), Open Data (OD) and crowdsourcing platforms (UNESCO) (Mičunović, M., Rako, S., & Feldvari, K., 2021).

The first part of our observations at ULSIT, Sofia, refers to the issue of DE; the second part investigates the degrees of implementation and modes of use of open educational resources; and the third part explores the issue of institutional support provided to departments, lecturers and students regarding DE and open educational resources. All three issues are assessed both in general and in the context of COVID-19 pandemic - the learning challenges, which we faced at AY 2019/2020 (summer semester) and AY 2020/2021.

3 RESULTS FROM SURVEY IMPLEMENTATION AT ULSIT

ULSIT has been a state higher education institution since 29th September 2010, it is a successor to the Library Institute, founded in 1950, and later transformed into the College of Library Studies and Information Technologies (3 April 2003). Nowadays, it has 163 lecturers, and 2390 students and delivers education in Bachelor, Master, and Doctoral degree programmes in four professional fields accredited by the National Evaluation and Accreditation Agency: Social Communications and Information Sciences, Cultural Heritage, History and Archaeology, Informatics and Computer Sciences and National Security in a full- and part-time training, as well as distance learning.

3.1 Digital Education (DE) during COVID-19 pandemic

The analyses reveal that at ULSIT, Sofia the following aspects of DE during COVID-19 pandemic are being implemented:

- digital repository of teaching and learning materials;
- live teaching sessions via Google Meet mainly together with Big Blue Button and Zoom;
- online courses via Moodle and ILIAS Learning Management Systems (LMS);
- recorded and archived teaching sessions;

- online examination and new ways of assessment and evaluation of student's work;
- online communication with students;
- online communication and collaboration with local and distant colleagues and fellow educators.

In the learning process at ULSIT's specialties the following DE techniques/strategies are used during COVID-19 pandemic: adaptive or personalized learning; blended learning with uses of multiple methods to deliver learning hybrid by combining face-to-face interactions with online activities; fully online learning via Moodle and ILIAS LMS; mobile learning as a variety of e-learning that is based on using handheld devices such as tablets and smartphones to access learning content and gamification (based on NAVIGATE Erasmus+ Project learning games) (Navigate, 2021).

Two approaches in the implementation of problem-based learning are experienced. In some disciplines lecturers use problem-based learning understanding as a student-centered approach to learning with groups of students working together to solve an open-ended problem thus supporting self-directed learning and strengthening of their communication and teamwork, research skills, information literacy, problem-solving skills, and critical thinking. Other courses were appropriate for project-based learning as a teaching method and a dynamic approach in which students actively engage in exploring real-world problems through personally meaningful projects while acquiring a deeper knowledge in the field.

We could summarize the use of the following tools for DE at ULSIT: learning management systems (Moodle, ILIAS, virtual classroom software Google Classroom); video conferencing tools (Big Blue Button, Zoom, MS Teams, Google Meet); repositories (online subject repositories, vendor platforms with repository features); instant messaging apps (Viber, WhatsApp); social media (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube) and resources types such as: learning materials (documents, articles, videos, pictures, etc.); learning materials in OERs; e-textbooks etc.

The new didactic approaches in online education at ULSIT were implemented by increasing flexibility, by using platforms to share knowledge and skills, by focusing on learning activities and competencies, by increasing interaction with live online sessions, by providing clear structure and content of the online course (Kovatcheva, 2022). We used a coaching system providing regular online consultations and live online Q&A sessions to handle students' problems and monitoring the learning process. The teaching staff provided the course's customization, i.e. personalize and adapt the teaching and learning process to the students' needs. Lecturers use so called flipped classroom methodology with providing all material in the LMS and having shorter lectures and longer classroom activity instead of long lectures and homework, they could customize learning goals, apply flexibility in the course content or allow students different opportunities to show and demonstrate their knowledge and skills. We worked on real cases and there was a pool of learning activities related to students and the inquiry-based approach was supported by teachers as mentors. Recorded and archived teaching sessions (without or after editing process) were practiced regularly by the lecturers and were appreciated by students.

ULSIT's University Library was an active partner of DE in the pandemic period. Lecturers and students were able to obtain necessary library materials during library closures via innovative practices such as Bibliocar (personal delivery of books by car in Sofia city), electronic document delivery and other virtual library services; to communicate via Library Virtual Room every Friday for consultations and discussions with information specialists; to use e-library collections.

3.2 Implementation and modes of use of open educational resources

In January 2021, the Bulgarian Portal for Open Science (BPOS) was launched in line with the engagement to contribute in EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) and in the frame of realization of two national strategies - "Bulgaria National Roadmap for Research Infrastructure, 2017-2023" and "National Strategy for Development of Scientific Research in the Republic of Bulgaria 2017 – 2030: Better Science for Better Bulgaria" (Bulgaria, 2017; National Strategy, 2021). Scientists have exceptional importance for the implementation of the Open Science initiative. In the submitted National Plan for Development of the Initiative for Open Access in Bulgaria (2021-2025) special attention is dedicated to the researcher participation (National Plan, 2021). On institutional level at ULSIT popularization of the culture of sharing and the appropriate training were provided together with explanation of the individual benefits from open access, such as better dissemination of the results from research activities and opportunities for the optimization of the research process (Todorova, T., & Garvanova, M., 2021, p. 3824). From March 2021 to May 2022 the ULSIT academic staff contributed to BPOS with 498 publications, which are actively used in the learning process in the pandemic period, and beyond (Bulgarian, 2021).

There are not LIS OERs on Bulgarian up to now. The creation and implementation of OERs is not a popular practice and usually it is a result of an engaged individual lecturer. Since March 2021, as a partner of DECriS project, we have been motivated to translate and adapt in Bulgarian the LIS OER's created as an intellectual product in the frame of that project. Partially, in the learning process of specialties at Faculty of Information Sciences we used more than 30 OERs courses, developed mainly under the Erasmus+ projects, jointly with partners at EU projects, available on ULSIT website: <https://projects.unibit.bg/> (enter as a guest). Some of those projects were coordinated by ULSIT, such as: APIInno (2016), DigiThink (2018), IoTnuggets (2021). In these courses are used and developed the innovative training approaches. Few of the courses are developed by ULSIT academic staff for training of partners from different universities under the TEMPUS program.

The lessons learned from the COVID-19 crisis positioned the importance of using the OERs and the implementation of criteria for evaluation of OERs. Morganti and Towery (2020) designed Checklist for Evaluating OER to help instructors to evaluate OERs in terms of breadth of perspectives and accuracy, alignment, production quality, accessibility, student access, student engagement, cultural relevance and sensitivity, licensing, and adaptability.

3.3 Institutional support provided to departments, lecturers and students

In the pandemic period the shift to distance education was based on policy documents and procedure frameworks both on national and institutional level. Zahariev et al. (2021) study about the evolution in the regulatory framework for distance learning in a pandemic environment in Bulgaria concluded that the Covid-19 and the new regulation of distance learning pushed forward all Bulgarian universities on the road of fast digitalization and introduction of the most advanced e-learning technologies. Higher education institutions implement simultaneously the government policy for increasing the quality of education, the efficiency of the organization of the educational process and the administrative procedures. They underlined the positive impact of the new Ordinance on the state requirements for organizing distance learning in higher education in Bulgaria by the Ministry of Education and Science, published in the State Gazette in March 2021 (in force since September 1, 2021), which provides a new definition of the distance-learning form of higher education, specified in three separate paragraphs. It is defined that "a form of higher education in which students, teachers and administrators can be separated by location, but not necessarily by time, as the distance created is compensated by technologies, methods and means of e-learning". The role of digital technologies has been introduced: distance learning is realized through digital technologies for managing the learning process, based on a system of different type, location and time of use of human, material and information activities and resources. The process approach is integrated in teaching - to compensate for the distance, the higher schools model the respective educational and administrative activities as information processes and implement them through information and communication technologies (Ordinance as cited in Zahariev, A., Ivanova, P., Angelov, A. & Zaharieva, G., 2021, p. 18-19).

In ULSIT the relevant documents coordinated the process, such as orders by Rector and Rules and Recommendation documents at the Faculty of Librarianship and Cultural Heritage and the Faculty of Information Science for organizing the learning process in the conditions of a pandemic situation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The findings from the Survey, titled State-of-the-play of the use of OERs at European HEIs during the COVID-19 pandemic, implemented at University of Library Studies and Information Technologies, were presented to the colleagues and stakeholders, and could be used as the basis for further reflection on the institutional DE quality assurance policy and the improvement of the Quality of Education Management System.

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